

Spectrophotometric Study of the Complex Equilibria in Palladium-Chromeazurol S System

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The complex formation between palladium (II) and trisodium salt of 3''-sulpho-2'' : 6''-dichloro-3 : 3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxyfuchsonone-5 : 5'-dicarboxylic acid (Chromeazurol S; abbr. CAS) has been studied spectrophotometrically. The formation of 2 : 1, 2 : 2 and 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes has been inferred by analysing the spectral data, using Asmus's straight line and the continuous variation method. The stability constants of the chelates (ionic strength 0.1M NaNO₃; temperature 25°) are $\log K_{(2,1)p}H_{3.5} = 9.80$, $\log K_{(2,2)p}H_{3.8} = 15.27$ and $\log K_{(1,1)p}H_{4.5} = 4.91$.

Several hydroxytriphenylmethane dyes have been studied for their chelating properties¹. Chelates involving CAS with Cu(II), Be(II), Mg(II), Cd(II), Al(III), Zr(IV), Fe(III), Pd(II), Th(IV), and U(VI) had been reported²⁻⁴ till 1964. Subsequently Dey *et al* also studied the CAS chelates of Ga(III), In(III), Ti(IV), Zr(IV) and Hf(IV), rare earth ions and some platinum metals⁵⁻¹². Langmyhr and Klausen¹³ carried out a detailed spectrophotometric investigation of Fe(III)-CAS system and inferred the formation of several complex species.

It was considered worthwhile to reinvestigate the Pd(II)-CAS system studied earlier¹⁴, with a view to investigating fully the various complex equilibria in the metal-dye system and the results are presented here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Instruments and Equipment : Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer. For measurements glass cells of thickness 10 mm or 30 mm were employed as necessary. L & N direct reading pH-meter, having glass and calomel electrode assembly and working on 220 volts/50 cycles stabilised a.c. mains, was used to measure and adjust the hydrogen ion concentration.

Materials : The tetrabasic acid (H₄CAS) was prepared from Chromeazurol S (B.D.H. Indicator)¹⁵, and dissolved to obtain a 1.0×10^{-3} M aqueous stock solution, which was suitably diluted.

An aqueous solution of palladous chloride (Johnson Matthey and Co., England) was prepared by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised by the usual method and a stock solution of 1.0×10^{-3} M was prepared.

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A stock solution of 2.0 *M* NaNO₃ was prepared by direct weighing of a B.D.H. AnalaR sample.

Investigation of the Chelate Formation :

Absorption Curves : Absorption curves were obtained for four series of solutions containing the reactants in varying mole ratios. The measurements were carried out in 10 mm cells against blanks containing the same amounts of inert salt and ligand at the same *pH*.

Fig. 1. Continuous Variations Curves
(*pH* = 3.8; 590 nm) $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

The concentration, composition and mode of addition of the solutions are given in table 1.

TABLE 1

Survey of solutions prepared for measurements of absorption curves

2.0 <i>M</i> NaNO ₃ (ml)	Mixtures of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ Pd(II) (ml)	$1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ H ₄ CAS (ml)	Mole ratio Pd (II) : H ₄ CAS
1.25	16	4	4 : 1
1.25	10	10	1 : 1
1.25	4	16	1 : 4
1.25	3.33	16.37	1 : 5

In the first, second and fourth series, the order of addition was : inert salt solution, palladium (II) solution and ligand solution. In the third series the ligand solution was added before the palladium (II) solution.

Within the *pH* range 2.6–3.9, a complex with an absorption maximum of 590 nm predominated in all series. This complex which appears to be comparatively stable—predominated irrespective of the mole ratio of the reactants and of the order of addition.

Within the pH range 4.0–5.5, a complex with an absorption maximum 600 nm was detected. Above pH 5.5, a complex with an absorption maximum 610 nm seemed to form. This complex appeared only in the presence of an excess of ligand.

Method of Continuous Variations: The method of continuous variations was employed to elucidate the composition of the two complexes having the absorption maxima 590 nm and 600 nm respectively. Fig. 1 and 2 represent Job's plot using difference in absorbance to determine the composition of the chelate at pH 3.8 and pH 4.5 respectively.

Fig. 2. Continuous Variations Curve
($pH = 4.5$; 600 nm) $c_2 = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

In the Fig. 1, the resulting curve showed the maximum at the mole fraction 0.5, indicating the presence of a complex $A_m B_n$ for which $m = n$. In addition, both the curve branches exhibited an inversion point and approached the limits parabolically. This type of curve, which has been discussed by Klausen and Langmyhr¹³ clearly demonstrated the presence of a complex for which $m = n > 1$.

Fig. 3. Straight-line Method (pH 3.5; 590 nm)
Ligand Varying; $a = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

In Fig. 2, the resulting curve showed the maximum at the mole fraction 0.5, indicating the presence of a complex A_mB_n , for which $m = n$. This curve does not exhibit the presence of a polynuclear complex. So the complex was inferred to be 1 : 1.

Fig. 4. Straight-Line Method (pH 3.8; 590 nm)
 (a) Metal Varying; $b = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$
 (b) Ligand Varying; $a = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

The Straight-line Method : This method was introduced by Asmus¹⁵ and was extended by Klausen and Langmyhr¹³.

Fig. 5. Straight-Line Method (pH 4.5; 600 nm)
 Ligand Varying; $a = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

The straight-line method was applied to a series of solutions at different pH . Table 2 surveys the series of solutions prepared, their pH and the wavelength of measurement, and the resulting curves are shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5.

TABLE 2

Survey of solutions prepared for the use of the straight-line method

Concentration of the reactant maintained constant $\times 10^5$ (M)	Concentration range of the reactant varied $\times 10^5$ (M)	pH	Measurement made at (nm)
1.0 Pd	1.0-6.0 H_4CAS	3.5	590
1.0 H_4CAS	1.0-7.0 Pd	3.8	590
1.0 Pd	1.0-6.0 H_4CAS	3.8	590
1.0 Pd	1.0-6.0 H_4CAS	4.5	600

*Method of Dey and Coworkers*¹⁶: This method has been applied to calculate the stability constants. The curves represented by Figs. 6 and 7 represent the experimental results at pH 3.8 and 4.5 respectively.

Fig. 6. Calculation of K (pH 3.8; 590 nm)

A $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

B $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composition of the Chelates: In the pH range 2.6-3.9, a purple coloured chelate, predominating in all mixtures, with an absorption maximum at 590 nm was detected. As the curve of continuous variations (Fig. 1) showed the presence of a chelate $Pd_m(CAS)_n$ for which $m = n > 1$, and the straight-line method (Fig. 4a) established the value of m to be 2, it was inferred that the complex species was definitely A_2B_2 , although the value of n was

found to be 1 (Fig. 4b). This is due to the fact that while determining the value of n by the straight-line method, an excess of the metal ion was present, while the ligand (in deficient quantity) was varying. It appears that initially a complex $\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})$ is formed which changes over to $\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})_2$ with increased quantity of the ligand (as was possible in the continuous variations method). Since an excess of the ligand was not available in the straight-line method (while determining the value of n), the complex remains $\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})$ in the system and could not change to $\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})_2$.

Fig. 7. Calculation of K ($\text{pH } 4.5$; 600 nm)

A $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

B $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

In the pH range ($4.0-5.5$), a blue coloured complex with an absorption maximum 600 nm was detected. The method of continuous variations (Fig. 2) showed this complex to be $1 : 1$. This was also supported by the straight-line, applied to a series of solutions containing excess of $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$ and varying the ligand for which a straight-line was obtained for $m = 1$ (Fig. 5). So the chelate is a monomer in this case. Above $\text{pH } 5.5$, a green coloured complex with absorption maximum 610 nm was detected. No comment regarding the composition and stability of this chelate has been possible on account of the fading of the colour. But it could be assumed that the value of n in this chelate was greater than 1, because this chelate appeared only in the presence of an excess of ligand.

The various species are shown in table 3.

Stability Constants of the Chelates : The experimental data from the methods employed were used to calculate the conditional stability constants.

$\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})$ -Chelate : The calculations were carried out by the straight-line method^{13,15,16}. Assuming the equilibrium

TABLE 3

Species in the system as a function of pH and mole ratio of the reactants

Mole Ratio Pd : H ₄ CAS in the mixture	pH	Species	Colour
4 : 1	2.6—3.9	[Pd(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (CAS) and Pd ₂ (CAS) ₂ ⁴⁻	Purple
	4.0—5.5	Pd(H ₂ O) ₂ (HCAS)-	Blue
1 : 1	2.6—3.9	[Pd(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (CAS) and Pd ₂ (CAS) ₂ ⁴⁻	Purple
	4.0—5.5	Pd(H ₂ O) ₂ (HCAS)-	Blue
1 : 4	2.6—3.9	[Pd(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (CAS) and Pd ₂ (CAS) ₂ ⁴⁻	Purple
	4.0—5.5	Pd(H ₂ O) ₂ (HCAS)-	Blue
	Above 5.5		Green
1 : 5	2.6—3.9	[Pd(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (CAS) and Pd ₂ (CAS) ₂ ⁴⁻	Purple
	4.0—5.5	Pd(H ₂ O) ₂ (HCAS)-	Blue
	Above 5.5		Green

it followed that conditional constant $K_{(2,1)H}$ could be calculated from the expression

$$K_{(2,1)H} = GV^2/4a_0v_0b_0$$

In this case, the value of G was found to be 2.5 ml⁻¹, which was derived from the Fig. 3. The other values are: pH = 3.5, $a_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $b_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $V = 100$ ml and $v_0 = 10$ ml. Therefore, $\log K_{(2,1)pH3.5} = 9.80$.

Pd₂(CAS)₂-Chelate: Assuming the equilibrium given above, the conditional constant $K_{(2,2)H}$ was calculated from the expression

$$K_{(2,2)H} = G/m^2(V/a_0v_0)^{m-1}(V/b_0)^n$$

The straight-line on the Fig. 5a relating to the 2 : 2 chelate gave two values for G (5.0 ml⁻² and 7.0 ml⁻²), and by introducing $m = n = 2$ and the experimental data: pH = 3.8, $a_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $b_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $V = 100$ ml and $v_0 = 10$ ml, the two values obtained for the conditional constant were $\log K_{(2,2)pH3.8} = 15.10$ and 15.24 respectively.

The conditional constant $K_{(2,2)H}$ was also calculated by the method of Dey and co-worker (Fig. 6).

Pd(CAS)-Chelate: In the presence of a monomer ($m = n = 1$), the conditional constant by the straight-line method is given by

$$K_{(1,1)H} = VG/b_0.$$

From Fig. 6, the value of G was found to be 0.8 ml^{-1} , by introducing the experimental data: $\text{pH} = 4.5$, $V = 100 \text{ ml}$, $b_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, the value for the conditional constant was: $\log K_{(1:1)\text{pH}4.5} = 4.90$.

From the Fig. 7, the calculations by the method of Dey *et al* have been made.

Table 4 summarizes the values of the stability constants of the various chelates.

TABLE 4

Stability constants of Pd(II)-CAS Chelates $\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaNO}_3)$; Temperature = 25°

Chelate	Calculations based on	log K	Average log K
$\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})$	Straight-line method	9.80	9.80
$\text{Pd}_2(\text{CAS})_2$	Straight-line method	15.17	
	Method of Dey <i>et al.</i>	15.36	15.27
$\text{Pd}(\text{CAS})$	Straight-line method	4.90	
	Method of Dey <i>et al.</i>	4.92	4.91

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